

The impact of technology on labour market outcomes of demographic groups in Europe

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Abstract

We study the age- and gender-specific labour market effects of two key modern technologies - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and robots - in 14 European countries between 2010-2018. To identify the causal effects of technology adoption, we utilise the variation of capital growth between industries and apply the instrumental variables strategy proposed by Acemoglu and Restrepo (2019). We find that the adoption of ICT and robots is beneficial for young and prime-aged women, as well as for older men. Negative effects on relative labour market outcomes are concentrated among older women and prime-aged men. Between 2010 and 2018, the growth of ICT capital played a visibly larger role in explaining changes in labour market outcomes than robot adoption.

Keywords: technological change, labour market effects, Europe

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1. Introduction

The use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and robots has been changing the world of work in the last few decades. Between 2000 and 2019, the real value of ICT capital per worker in Europe has increased by 91%, while the robot exposure, measured by the number of industrial robots per 1,000 workers, has increased by 140%. Robots and other labour-saving technologies can have important aggregate and compositional labour market effects. They can directly reduce employment as machines replace humans in performing certain tasks, resulting in a labour-saving effect. However, the product demand effect - i.e., an increase in activity thanks to a productivity-enhancing technology - and the demand spillover effect - i.e., demand for other sectors' output resulting from higher value added and incomes in the technology-adopting sector - can increase employment. Gregory, Salomons & Zierahn (2021) showed that the latter two effects have been dominant in Europe, leading to an overall positive employment effect of routine-replacing technologies. However, computers and other digital technologies have changed the structure of jobs tasks performed by humans, reducing the role of routine tasks and increasing the role of non-routine tasks, both within and across occupations (Autor, Levy & Murnane, 2003; Spitz-Oener, 2006). This has led to job and wage polarisation in developed countries (Goos, Manning & Salomons, 2014). This hollowing out of the middle-paid jobs has created winners and losers of technological progress. While a lot of attention has been paid to differences associated with education (Firpo, Fortin & Lemieux, 2011; Gathmann & Schönberg, 2010), the age- and gender dimensions of exposure to new technologies have not been comprehensively studied.

In this paper, we fill this gap and study the age- and gender-specific labour market effects of two key modern technologies - ICT and robots - in a large group of European countries. There are two main reasons why the effects of technology adoption can differ for younger and older workers. On the one hand, technological change can reduce returns to old skills related to technology that become obsolete, and increase returns to new skills related to emerging technology (Fillmore & Hall, 2021). As older workers tend to have skills that complement older technologies, and their expected returns from an investment in new skills are lower than those of younger workers, the older workers can be more affected by technological change. Indeed, older people (aged 55-64) in the OECD countries tend to have lower ICT and analytical skills and are

less likely to use information-processing skills at work than younger individuals (the Programme for the International Assessment of Adult Competencies – PIAAC – data). On the other hand, older workers are more likely to benefit from insider power, and, as such, may be more protected from changes than younger workers, who are often outsiders or labour market entrants. Indeed, there is evidence that the de-routinisation of work in Europe has affected younger workers to a larger extent (Lewandowski *et al.*, 2020), and that industrial robots in Germany have reduced the labour market prospects of younger workers (Dauth *et al.*, 2021). The gender dimension is also relevant. On one hand, routine-replacing technologies increase returns to social skills which women tend to have a comparative advantage in (Deming, 2017) so they benefit more from ICT adoption than men (Jerbashian, 2019). On the other hand, women lag behind men in skills complementary to new technologies: women are less likely than men to study in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) college programmes (Delaney & Devereux, 2019) and exhibit lower numeracy skills (Rebollo-Sanz & De la Rica, 2020).

Our first contribution is to disentangle both gender- and age-specific effects in the labour market impact of new technologies. We focus on three key labour market outcomes of demographic groups: share in employment, average wage, and share in the wage bill. This allows us to identify key consequences of technology adoption for particular demographic groups: men and women aged 20-29, 30-49, 50-59, 60 years or more.

Our second contribution is to distinguish between the effects of two key types of routine-replacing technologies: ICT and robots.¹ We measure ICT capital with Eurostat data, and robots with International Federation of Robotics (IFR, 2017) data. Both types of technology are measured at a finely disaggregated sector level and we merged them with the worker-level data of the EU Structure of Earnings Survey (EU-SES) which allow us to calculate labour market outcomes of demographic groups. Due to data availability, our sample includes 14 European countries between 2010 and 2018.² To obtain causal effects, we make two methodological choices.

¹ Previous literature has been largely focused on the aggregate effects of ICT and robots. While these routine-replacing technologies had a direct, negative effect on employment in Europe (substitution), once the demand and spillover effects are accounted for, the total effect has been positive (Gregory, Salomons & Zierahn, 2021). Robots reduced aggregate employment in the US (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2020) which fuelled fears that automation will to mass joblessness. In Europe though, the labour market effects of robots have been benign: robots reduced employment in manufacturing at the expense of higher employment in services but were neutral for total employment in Germany (Dauth *et al.*, 2021). They have reduced the risk of job loss and improved chances of job finding in the Eastern and Southern European countries, but have minimal effect on labour market flows in Western European countries (Bachmann *et al.*, 2022).

² Belgium, Czechia, Germany, Estonia, Greece, Spain, Finland, France, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, and Sweden.

First, we estimate models of demographic groups' outcomes within sectors, so we focus on the direct effect of technology on labour market outcomes.³ Second, we apply the instrumental variable (IV) methodology. As an instrument, we use the average exposure to ICT or robots in comparable countries – this method has been applied to robots by, e.g., (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2020; Dauth *et al.*, 2021; Bachmann *et al.*, 2022).

We find a heterogeneous impact of technology adoption on demographic groups. Growth in the exposure to ICT capital is beneficial for relative labour market outcomes of women aged 20-49 and for older men. We find negative effects of ICT capital growth for older women, and for men aged 30-59 (the latter result is not precisely estimated). Robots adoption, in turn, harms labour market outcomes of men aged 30-49 and women aged 50-64, whereas women aged 20-29 benefit from increased exposure to robots. Historically, the growth of ICT capital played a significantly larger role in explaining changes in labour market outcomes than robots adoption.

2. Data and descriptive statistics

2.1. Data and definitions

To measure labour market outcomes, we use worker-level data from the EU Structure of Earnings Survey (EU-SES). It is the most reliable source of cross-country data on wages in the EU, as these are reported by firms. Another advantage of SES is that the sectoral structure - needed to assign data on technology - is at the 2-digit NACE level which is more detailed than in other EU microdata, e.g., Labour Force Survey. An important limitation of the EU-SES is that it does not cover firms with less than 10 workers. However, we study the effects on automation and ICT capital – so technologies that are less often used by micro firms than by firms with at least 10 workers. The EU-SES data have already been used to study the labour market effects of automation, for instance by Aksoy, Özcan and Philipp (2021). The EU-SES data are collected every four years.

We account for two types of technologies: ICT and industrial robots. Data on both are available at the country x sector level. The data on ICT capital are obtained from Eurostat. We add net stocks of three types of capital: computer hardware, telecommunications equipment, and computer software and databases. We use data expressed in chain-linked volumes to account for the systematic price decline of the ICT capital. We use all countries, for which sectoral distribu-

³ Focusing on sectors to assess causal effects of technology is common. We follow (Graetz & Michaels, 2018) who used sector regressions to find that robot adoption has increased GDP, labour productivity, and wages, and Jerbashian (2019) who studied within-sector effect of IT technology adoption and found negative impact on the share of middle-waged occupations.

tion of the ICT capital is available. For Germany and Spain, we use data from EU-KLEMS 2019 release.⁴

The data on robots come from the International Federation of Robotics (IFR, 2017), which provides annual information on the current stock of industrial robots across countries, broken down by industries. The data are based on consolidated information provided by nearly all industrial robot suppliers. The IFR ensures that the data are reliable and internationally comparable. According to the definition by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO 8373:201), an industrial robot is an *'automatically controlled, reprogrammable, multipurpose manipulator, programmable in three or more axes, which can be either fixed in place or mobile for use in industrial automation applications'*. We use Eurostat aggregate employment data to calculate exposure to both robots and the ICT capital.

Because of data availability, our study period is 2010-2018. The NACE Rev. 2 classification used by Eurostat in the EU-SES data from 2010 allows a fine matching of technology variables. However, the earlier waves of EU-SES used the NACE Rev. 1 classification, which can only be mapped into the NACE Rev. 2 classification at the broad sector level that does not capture important differences in technology use between finely defined sectors. In particular, major business services sections present in the NACE Rev. 2 classification cannot be retrieved from NACE Rev. 1.⁵

Furthermore, to control for globalisation, we use the OECD Trade in Value Added data to construct a measure of sectors' participation in global value chains. We compute this measure as foreign value added in exports divided by total sectoral output.

Our sample of countries with all these data available consists of 14 European countries: Belgium, Czechia, Germany, Estonia, Greece, Spain, Finland, France, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, and Sweden. The average number of sectors per country is 22, with some differences arising due to the aggregation schemes in the SES.

The unit of analysis is a demographic group defined based on age - we distinguish four age groups (20-29, 30-49, 50-59, 60+) - and gender, in a given sector and country. In total, we have 936 country x sector observations for each demographic group. We drop groups with fewer

⁴ KLEMS data end in 2017 for Germany and in 2016 for Spain. We impute values for 2018 using aggregate growth of ICT capital from Eurostat.

⁵ For example, NACE rev. 1 category 70_to_73 contains major parts of the four NACE rev. 2 sections: L – Real Estate Activities, N – Administrative and Support Service Activities, J – Information and communication, and M – Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities.

than 15 observations. The remaining number of worker-level observations in our sample is 21.3 million. On average, a demographic group contains 2,934 observations.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	Mean	p10	p25	p50	p75	p90
Employment share, women 20-29	8.0	2.1	4.2	7.6	11.4	14.3
Employment share, women 30-49	25.1	10.3	17.5	25.9	32.8	38.1
Employment share, women 50-59	11.4	4.0	6.6	9.9	15.6	21.6
Employment share, women 60+	3.8	0.7	1.3	2.6	5.4	8.7
Employment share, men 20-29	9.0	2.9	5.3	8.6	11.7	15.1
Employment share, men 30-49	27.3	10.0	19.7	26.8	35.0	44.3
Employment share, men 50-59	11.6	4.9	7.1	10.4	16.3	20.4
Employment share, men 60+	4.0	1.4	2.2	3.5	5.3	7.4
Relative wages, women 20-29	78.8	65.2	71.6	78.9	85.3	91.3
Relative wages, women 30-49	95.2	88.1	91.2	95.4	98.9	102.3
Relative wages, women 50-59	96.4	83.1	90.1	97.3	102.2	107.0
Relative wages, women 60+	96.0	77.4	85.3	95.1	103.3	114.3
Relative wages, men 20-29	83.4	68.8	75.4	82.2	91.0	100.2
Relative wages, men 30-49	111.6	100.4	103.6	109.4	117.4	126.9
Relative wages, men 50-59	118.7	101.4	108.8	116.7	127.8	139.5
Relative wages, men 60+	122.0	94.9	106.3	118.0	132.8	153.3
ICT capital per worker (thousand EUR)	5.1	0.7	1.2	2.4	4.9	9.4
Robots per thousand employees	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.8
GVC participation	4.5	0.0	0.2	1.8	5.3	13.8

Note: Employment shares of all demographic groups sum up to 100 in each country-sector-year cell. Relative wage is the mean wage of a demographic group in a given sector as % of the mean sectoral wage.

Table 1 reports descriptive statistics for this sample. Typically, more than half of employment at the sector level is composed of people aged 30-49. Descriptive statistics also tend to confirm a substantial gender wage gap in all age groups. ICT exposure significantly varies across the whole sample, while robots are concentrated only in selected sectors (mostly manufacturing).

2.2. Descriptive evidence

We report correlations between four-year changes in the stocks of ICT capital (Figure 1) or robots (Figure 2) with the four-year changes in the demographic groups' shares in sectors' total wage bill. We find that labour market outcomes of prime-aged men are negatively related to both types of technology. Also, the adoption of ICT technology is negatively correlated with outcomes of older women and positively related with the outcomes of young and prime-aged women. However, these findings do not account for various types of endogeneity, and therefore cannot be interpreted in causal terms.

Figure 1. ICT capital growth and changes in the shares of wage bill

Source: Own elaboration based on EU-SES and Eurostat

Figure 2. Growth in robots exposure and changes in the shares of wage bill

Source: Own elaboration based on EU-SES and IFR

3. Methodology

Here, we outline our estimation framework and causal approach and explain the methodology of post-estimation analyses to quantify their economic significance.

3.1. Estimation framework and instruments

We focus on three labour key market outcomes of demographic groups: share in employment (based on the number of employees), wages relative to the average wage, and share in the wage bill. The third outcome is the consequence of the former two and sums up the impact. We study the impact of two technological shocks: industrial robots and the ICT capital. Our identification strategy relies on the variation of technological capital growth across sectors and countries.

Following Graetz and Michaels (2018) and Acemoglu and Restrepo (2019), we calculate robot exposure as the number of robots per thousand workers at the sector level, ($R_{c,s,t}$). Analogously, we compute exposure to ICT capital, ($I_{c,s,t}$), as the net stock of ICT capital and software expressed in real terms (in 2015 euros) per worker. We use the 2010 employment (the first year of our sample) as a numerator. This ensures that variation in the explanatory variables over time reflects the acquisition of selected assets, and is independent of changes in employment (which could be endogenous to capital growth).

First, we estimate the following OLS regressions for each demographic group d :

$$\Delta y_{c,s,d,t} = \beta_1 \Delta I_{c,s,t} + \beta_2 \Delta R_{c,s,t} + \beta_3 \Delta GVC_{c,s,t} + \beta_4 Edu_{c,s,d,t-1} + \rho_{c,t} + \epsilon_{c,s,d,t} \quad (1)$$

where y stands for the share of a demographic group in the total wage bill, its share in employment, or its relative wages; $GVC_{c,s,t}$ is the foreign value added in exports divided by total sectoral output; $Edu_{c,s,d,t-1}$ is the lagged share of tertiary educated persons in a demographic group relative to the sectoral average; $\rho_{c,t}$ denotes country-year fixed effects; t takes two levels: 2014 and 2018, whereas 2010 is the initial reference period.

By including country-year fixed effects, we control for all aggregate changes in labour supply of demographic groups, as well as institutional developments that may affect labour market outcomes. We also control for sector-specific participation in global value chains, which saw substantial increases in the analysed period. Some variation in labour market outcomes of demographic groups may be explained by their initial average educational attainment. We express it in relative terms, as the average percentage of tertiary educated people is sector-specific.

As the explanatory variables of interest might be endogenous to labour market outcomes,⁶ we apply the instrumental variable method to obtain the causal effects of technology. We instrument exposure to both robots and ICT capital. In each case, we follow Bachmann *et al.* (2022) and generalise the ‘technology frontier’ instrument previously applied by (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2020) and Dauth *et al.* (2021). We instrument the robot (ICT) exposure in sector s , country c , and year t with the average robot (ICT) exposure in other European countries. For example, instrument for robots adoption, $R_{c,s,t}^{iv}$, is given by:

$$R_{c,s,t}^{iv} = \sum_{k, k \neq c}^K \frac{ROB_{k,s,t}}{EMP_{k,s,t_0}} \quad (2)$$

where $ROB_{k,s,t}$ is the stock of industrial robots in country k , sector s , and year t , and EMP_{k,s,t_0} is employment level in thousands in country k , and sector s in 2010

We re-estimate equation (1) using two-stage least squares (2SLS). The relevance of instruments is confirmed by the Stock-Yogo (2005) test for weak instruments. We use standardised weights (based on 2010 employment structures) which give every country in the sample an equal weight.

3.2. Counterfactual analysis

To assess the economic impact of technology adoption on relative labour market outcomes, we conduct a counterfactual historical analysis. We focus on the shares in employment and in the wage bill. We do not report counterfactual analysis for relative wages, as it would be based on statistically insignificant estimates. In the counterfactual scenario, in each country and sector, we keep the ICT and robot exposures constant after 2010.

In the first step, we use coefficients from the 2SLS estimation (equation 1) and actual values of all variables entering the second stage of the estimation to calculate the predicted changes in the employment/wage bill shares of demographic groups. In the second step, for each demographic group we predict two counterfactual employment/wage bill shares, one assuming no changes in the exposure to the ICT capital, and the other no changes in the robot exposure. For that purpose, we use the same coefficients as in the first step. In the third step, we express the effects of each technology as the percentage points difference in the employment/wage bill shares between the model-predicted and counterfactual employment. As in the regression analysis, each country is given equal weight.

⁶ In particular, firms’ decisions to invest in technology may depend on the availability of workers, labour costs, etc.

4. Results

In this section, we present our econometric results. This is followed by the counterfactual analysis, which assesses the economic significance of our findings.

4.1. The impact of technology adoption on labour market outcomes

First, we report the effects of technology adoption on demographic groups' employment shares (Table 2). We find that both types of technology have positive effects on the employment of young women and negative effects on women aged 60 and above. Growth of the ICT capital by one thousand EUR per worker leads to the employment share of young women being 0.13 pp higher (p -value = 0.051), and the employment share of older women being lower by 0.2 pp. Each additional robot per one thousand workers increases the employment share of young women by 0.26 pp and decreases the employment share of older women by 0.17 pp.

For prime-aged men, we find a significant negative effect of robots adoption, with one additional robot per thousand workers reducing their employment share by 0.31 pp. In contrast, for men aged 50-59 robots have a positive (but less precisely estimated) employment effect. We also find positive effects of ICT capital for prime-aged women and men aged 60 and above.

We do not find statistically significant effects of technology adoption on relative wages (Table 3). For prime-aged men robots adoption has positive impact on average wages (p -value = 0.061). However, this may be a result of negative employment effects being concentrated at the lower end of the income distribution. Coefficients on the ICT capital are positive for women of all ages. Contrary, the wage effects of ICT capital seem to be negative for men (except for older men).

Table 2. The effect of technological change on the employment shares of demographic groups

	Women, OLS	Women, 2SLS	Men, OLS	Men, 2SLS
A: Age 20-29				
Δ ICT capital	0.064*** (0.022)	0.131* (0.067)	0.013 (0.027)	-0.004 (0.076)
Δ Robots	0.102*** (0.026)	0.258*** (0.087)	0.017 (0.034)	-0.121 (0.078)
No. of Observations	588	588	610	610
B: Age 30-49				
Δ ICT capital	0.044 (0.029)	0.196* (0.105)	0.004 (0.057)	-0.121 (0.120)
Δ Robots	0.057 (0.036)	0.098 (0.089)	-0.149** (0.072)	-0.310** (0.154)
No. of Observations	617	617	622	622
C: Age 50-59				
Δ ICT capital	-0.02 (0.022)	0 (0.065)	-0.063 (0.046)	-0.095 (0.089)
Δ Robots	-0.018 (0.020)	-0.039 (0.055)	-0.003 (0.038)	0.158* (0.094)
No. of Observations	608	608	620	620
D: Age 60+				
Δ ICT capital	-0.046*** (0.012)	-0.198*** (0.052)	-0.002 (0.010)	0.080* (0.045)
Δ Robots	-0.054** (0.021)	-0.166** (0.072)	0.02 (0.015)	0.044 (0.041)
No. of Observations	534	534	588	588
Maximal size distortions of a Wald statistic based on Stock-Yogo (2005) weak instruments test		<10%		<10%

Note: The table presents the estimated coefficients of the OLS and 2SLS regressions. Standard errors (in brackets) are clustered at the country-sector level. The dependent variable is a four-year change in the demographic group's share (in %) in total sector employment.

Δ ICT capital is the four-year change in the ICT and software capital stock (in thousand Euro, constant prices) divided by employment as of 2010.

Δ Robots is the four-year change in the number of industrial robots per 1,000 workers, where employment is fixed in 2010. Country-year fixed effects included. We also control for the change in the GVC participation and for the lagged share of tertiary-educated workers in the demographic group relative to the sector's average. For 2SLS, Δ Robots and Δ ICT capital are instrumented using the growth of these types of capital in other European countries. Results of the Stock-Yogo (2005) test for weak instruments are based on Kleibergen-Paap rk Wald F statistic, which is robust to heteroskedasticity.

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Source: authors' calculations based on the EU-SES, Eurostat, IFR, OECD TiVA and EU-KLEMS data

Table 3. The effect of technological change on the relative wages of demographic groups

	Women, OLS	Women, 2SLS	Men, OLS	Men, 2SLS
A: Age 20-29				
Δ ICT capital	0.04 (0.069)	0.178 (0.261)	-0.009 (0.057)	-0.145 (0.196)
Δ Robots	0.042 (0.070)	0.17 (0.229)	-0.039 (0.071)	0.068 (0.227)
No. of Observations	588	588	610	610
B: Age 30-49				
Δ ICT capital	-0.005 (0.046)	0.194 (0.202)	-0.001 (0.037)	-0.213 (0.193)
Δ Robots	0.111* (0.060)	0.088 (0.196)	0.187** (0.075)	0.373* (0.199)
No. of Observations	617	617	622	622
C: Age 50-59				
Δ ICT capital	0.302*** (0.103)	0.191 (0.162)	0.163 (0.169)	-0.371 (0.260)
Δ Robots	-0.013 (0.078)	-0.121 (0.206)	0.033 (0.120)	-0.286 (0.271)
No. of Observations	608	608	620	620
D: Age 60+				
Δ ICT capital	0.382* (0.231)	0.36 (0.449)	0.223 (0.209)	0.471 (0.383)
Δ Robots	-0.026 (0.227)	0.123 (0.511)	-0.128 (0.227)	0.292 (0.497)
No. of Observations	534	534	588	588
Maximal size distortions of a Wald statistic based on Stock-Yogo (2005) weak instruments test		<10%		<10%

Note: The table presents the estimated coefficients of the OLS and 2SLS regressions. Standard errors (in brackets) are clustered at the country-sector level. The dependent variable is a four-year change in the demographic group's average wage as % of the sector's average.

Δ ICT capital is the four-year change in the ICT and software capital stock (in thousand Euro, constant prices) divided by employment as of 2010.

Δ Robots is the four-year change in the number of industrial robots per 1,000 workers, where employment is fixed in 2010. Country-year fixed effects included. We also control for the change in the GVC participation and for the lagged share of tertiary-educated workers in the demographic group relative to the sector's average. For 2SLS, Δ Robots and Δ ICT capital are instrumented using the growth of these types of capital in other European countries. Results of the Stock-Yogo (2005) test for weak instruments are based on Kleibergen-Paap rk Wald F statistic, which is robust to heteroskedasticity.

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Source: authors' calculations based on the EU-SES, Eurostat, IFR, OECD TiVA and EU-KLEMS data

Now, we turn to the effects on the shares in the wage bill (Table 4). This outcome variable is a result of two previously discussed ones, but it also accounts for possible changes in average hours worked by different demographic groups. As in the analysis of employment effects, both ICT capital and robots have a positive impact on labour market outcomes of young women and a negative impact on women aged 60 and above. However, we also find that the overall effect of

ICT capital is significantly positive for prime-aged women and men aged 60 and above. Another important finding is that robots adoption has a negative effect (though insignificant) on prime-aged men's share in the total wage bill. Thus, positive effects on average hourly wages do not compensate for the negative employment effects among this group.

Table 4. The effect of technological change on the shares of demographic groups in the wage bill

	Women, OLS	Women, 2SLS	Men, OLS	Men, 2SLS
A: Age 20-29				
Δ ICT capital	0.045*** (0.017)	0.116** (0.055)	0.003 (0.022)	0.009 (0.062)
Δ Robots	0.069*** (0.021)	0.171*** (0.061)	0 (0.030)	-0.124 (0.076)
No. of Observations	588	588	610	610
B: Age 30-49				
Δ ICT capital	0.044* (0.026)	0.207** (0.104)	-0.006 (0.054)	-0.153 (0.142)
Δ Robots	0.058* (0.032)	0.096 (0.086)	-0.111 (0.068)	-0.22 (0.164)
No. of Observations	617	617	622	622
C: Age 50-59				
Δ ICT capital	-0.001 (0.021)	0.033 (0.064)	-0.048 (0.046)	-0.11 (0.110)
Δ Robots	-0.019 (0.020)	-0.049 (0.057)	0.005 (0.041)	0.128 (0.100)
No. of Observations	608	608	620	620
D: Age 60+				
Δ ICT capital	-0.040*** (0.011)	-0.172*** (0.047)	0.004 (0.012)	0.109** (0.049)
Δ Robots	-0.051*** (0.019)	-0.153** (0.068)	0.018 (0.019)	0.058 (0.049)
No. of Observations	534	534	588	588
Maximal size distortions of a Wald statistic based on Stock-Yogo (2005) weak instruments test		<10%		<10%

Note: The table presents the estimated coefficients of the OLS and 2SLS regressions. Standard errors (in brackets) are clustered at the country-sector level. The dependent variable is a four-year change in the demographic group's share (in %) in total sector wages.

Δ ICT capital is the four-year change in the ICT and software capital stock (in thousand Euro, constant prices) divided by employment as of 2010.

Δ Robots is the four-year change in the number of industrial robots per 1,000 workers, where employment is fixed in 2010. Country-year fixed effects included. We also control for the change in the GVC participation and for the lagged share of tertiary-educated workers in the demographic group relative to the sector's average. For 2SLS, Δ Robots and Δ ICT capital are instrumented using the growth of these types of capital in other European countries. Results of the Stock-Yogo (2005) test for weak instruments are based on Kleibergen-Paap rk Wald F statistic, which is robust to heteroskedasticity.

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Source: authors' calculations based on the EU-SES, Eurostat, IFR, OECD TiVA and EU-KLEMS data.

Our results are consistent with economic theory. The positive effects of ICT capital on women's labour market outcomes are in line with the finding of (Deming 2017) that women benefit from the adoption of ICT technologies due to their advantage in social skills, which are not substitutable by ICT capital. The negative effects of ICT capital on older women may be explained by lower IT literacy in this group. Given that prime-aged men in manufacturing often perform routine manual tasks, the negative employment effects of robots adoption for this group suggest that robots have a labour-replacing effect.

4.2. Counterfactual analysis of the labour market outcomes

On average, employment shares of young and prime-aged women in 2018 were higher by, respectively, 0.38 pp and 0.37 pp than in the counterfactual scenario of no technology adoption in the 2010-2018 period (Figure 3). For young women, the effect of ICT capital (0.20 pp) is slightly larger than the effect of robots adoption (0.18 pp). In contrast, for prime-aged women, the effects of ICT capital (0.30 pp) were much more important than robots adoption (0.07 pp). The difference between the historical and counterfactual employment share of older women is substantial (especially given their overall low employment share) and amounts to (-0.39) pp. It is mainly driven by the adoption of ICT capital (-0.29 pp). Negative effects of technology adoption are also observed among prime-aged men (-0.40 pp), with a slightly larger role of robots adoption (-0.22 pp). For older men, the positive effect amounts to 0.15 pp and is mostly attributable to the ICT technology (0.12 pp).

Figure 3. Effects of technology adoption on employment shares, pp

Note: The difference in the employment shares of demographic groups between the historical scenario and the counterfactual scenario of no increase in the ICT and robots exposure in the period 2010 - 2018.

Source: authors' calculations based on the EU-SES, Eurostat, IFR, OECD TiVA and EU-KLEMS data

The share in the wage bill of young and prime-aged women increased due to technology adoption by, respectively, 0.30 pp and 0.39 pp (Figure 4). The positive effect for older men amounts to 0.21 pp. If not for technology adoption, the share of prime-aged men in the wage bill would be larger by 0.39 pp, and the share of older women by 0.35 pp. In the period of our analysis, the majority of changes in the labour market outcomes were attributable to ICT capital growth, with robots adoption having a smaller impact.

Figure 4. Effects of technology adoption on shares in wage bill, pp

Note: The difference in the wage bill shares of demographic groups between the historical scenario and the counterfactual scenario of no increase in the ICT and robots exposure in the period 2010 - 2018.

Source: authors' calculations based on the EU-SES, Eurostat, IFR, OECD TiVA and EU-KLEMS data

In Appendix, we report the results of counterfactual analyses conducted for each country separately. Variation of results between countries stems from two factors: (i) country-specific average growth of ICT and robots exposures (captured in the first stage regressions by country-year fixed effects), (ii) differences in sectoral structures of the economies. Czechia and Germany stand out with the large role of robots adoption, while for France, Finland and Norway almost all effects on demographic groups are due to increased exposure to the ICT capital. The size of the effects also varies substantially between countries.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we have analysed the impact of technology adoption on relative labour market outcomes of eight demographic groups. We aimed to assess the effects of two key modern technologies – ICT and robots, on three labour market outcomes: shares in employment, relative wages, and shares in the total wage bill. We focused on the within-sector outcomes of demographic groups and used the between-sector variance in technology adoption to identify its causal effects. Our sample is based on 14 European countries in the 2010-2018 period.

We found that technology adoption has significant effects on employment shares of various demographic groups, while the effects on relative wages are statistically insignificant. Technology adoption improves relative labour market outcomes of young and prime-aged women, as well as of older men. Demographic groups vulnerable to technological progress include prime-aged men and older women. The two analysed technologies have different effects among various demographic groups. For example, only robot exposure is statistically significant in explaining employment shares of prime-aged men, while for prime-aged women it is the ICT capital that has a significant impact. In most countries of our sample, the ICT capital is a more important driver of changes in relative labour market outcomes.

Our results help to understand the future of demographic-specific challenges, such as youth unemployment, gender wage gap, or the need for increased labour market participation of older people. Technology adoption is bound to continue, so we may expect to observe in the near future similar trends as in the period of our study. The demographic distribution of winners and losers should be taken into account when calibrating public policies, for example, subsidies for education or labour taxes.

Appendices

Appendix A Employment effects of technology adoption by country, pp

Estonia, women

Estonia, men

Greece, women

Greece, men

Spain, women

Spain, men

Finland, women

Finland, men

France, women

France, men

Italy, women

Italy, men

Lithuania, women

Lithuania, men

Latvia, women

Latvia, men

Netherlands, women

Netherlands, men

Norway, women

Norway, men

Sweden, women

Sweden, men

Note: The difference in the employment shares of demographic groups between the historical scenario and the counterfactual scenario of no increase in the ICT and robots exposure in the period 2010 - 2018.

Source: authors' calculations based on the EU-SES, Eurostat, IFR, OECD TiVA and EU-KLEMS data

Appendix B Effects of technology adoption on shares in wage bill by country, pp

Estonia, women

Estonia, men

Greece, women

Greece, men

Spain, women

Spain, men

Finland, women

Finland, men

France, women

France, men

Italy, women

Italy, men

Lithuania, women

Lithuania, men

Latvia, women

Latvia, men

Netherlands, women

Netherlands, men

Note: The difference in the wage bill shares of demographic groups between the historical scenario and the counterfactual scenario of no increase in the ICT and robots exposure in the period 2010 - 2018.
Source: authors' calculations based on the EU-SES, Eurostat, IFR, OECD TiVA and EU-KLEMS data

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